

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Zero-shot Singing Voice Conversion

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Dedication

To those who suffered in the crazy times of COVID-19...

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Abstract

The task of Singing Voice Conversion(SVC) is to transform the voice of one singer(source) to someone else voice(target) yet preserving the content. Voice Conversion(VC) is well studied for speech but a relatively less explored topic in the context of the singing voice. While VC involves both changes in timbre and expression, modeled via fundamental frequency(F0) and timing; in the case of singing, the timing and pitch are constrained by a musical score and thereby, common algorithms designed for speech only, cannot be used directly to transform singing voice due to the lack of constraint on the melody in the system. We adapt a recently proposed state of the art system for speech VC to the case of singing VC. The system takes as input audio samples of the source and target singers and separates the content to preserve(lyrics, F0, and rhythm) from the singer-dependent content to transform(timbre). Then, the conversion is realized by re-synthesizing lyrics and melody of the source singer with the target singer's timbre which is encoded using neural network embeddings. Thus, our system performs timbre conversion only and preserves the melody and expression from the source track. But we also try to perform zero-shot voice conversion which is a special case of VC when converting happens between voices that were not present in the training data i.e, conversion can be done between any two voices. We focus as well on how various algorithms for generating speaker/singer embeddings affects the quality of our system in the context of zero-shot SVC.

Keywords: singing voice, voice conversion, zero-shot conversion

Chapter 1

Motivation

1.1 Introduction

Voice is the first and most common musical instrument. People spend years mastering the skills of the professional singing and there is no clear end there – once you reach a certain level, there is always room for building a unique singing style and improving the skills in general. To put it short: singing can be hard and time-consuming. That is probably the main reason why singing voice synthesizers were invented in the very first place. Having a never-tiring, perfectly singing, and cheap singer would be a dream for a music producer. Luckily for poor producers, there is VOCALOID¹ that has even more than one a never-tiring singer in their software. With the help of VOCALOID, a music producer can generate audio of a perfect singing voice given a certain music score.

On the other side of this situation – singers – who want to sing perfectly and do not suffer from hundreds of attempts to sing ideally. In this case, other solutions made specifically for vocals audios allow us to edit them. Using this software though might help singers with trying fewer attempts but the learning curve to be able to use this software, along with hours of editing the audio can be not less problematic as learning how to sing properly.

¹<https://www.vocaloid.com/en/>

Thus, the ultimate solution is a combination of both methods: voice synthesis and voice audio editing. A software that can take audio recordings of a singer and synthesize the ideal version of them based on the given musical score. The usage is simple: a singer sings as she or he can, then the software automatically analyze the audio and synthesize the audio with the voice of the singer. This is a voice-cloning technology that performs voice synthesis with the timbre analyzed from the audio of the given speaker. This is great! This is something that most of the singers would kill for. But, we, can do even better.

Theoretically, a singer **A** likes how she sings, and the voice synthesis helps a great deal. Albeit, in some songs, she feels something is wrong, the voice doe snot sounds as she wanted or imagined. "Fear not", we say, as we could resort to the voice conversion technologies. In that case, singer **A** who wants to sound like singer **B** could find examples of singing recordings from the singer **B** and provide them to the voice conversion system. That system would be similar to our ultimate solution because it synthesizes and clones voices but additionally to that, the target voice can be not of the original singer. That final solution is an example of a Singing Voice Conversion(SVC). SVC can be used not only to help singers that are not satisfied with their voices but in other creative and commercial applications. For instance, a voice in a song can be converted to the listener's voice to create a deeply personalized music experience. Or, a singer could sell its voice timbre to a software company that develops SVC solutions and receive royalties whenever someone uses its voice.

Another point of view on SVC applications is what part of voice gets converted. What is a successful Singing Voice Conversion after all? In the case of singing, voice has 4 parts that convey information: text, timbre, pitch, and rhythm. If we want to convert someone's singing to another voice we should keep the textual information from the source audio, otherwise, the conversion does not make sense. The rest three parts can be converted solely or all together leading to different goals and results. In the next examples, we assume the text part stays of the source audio. For example, if we convert only the timbre part, perceptually it should be enough to say that singer

has changed. This type of conversion would ideally fit the application described before, where a singer wants to sound different yet preserving its uniqueness in terms of melody and singing style. But what if a singer wants to change specifically the singing style but keep the timbre? In that case, the conversion would mostly happen with the pitch and rhythm components, which is more appropriate to call singing style conversion then. Finally, all the three parts could be converted together and that, luckily, would be perceived as the target singer singing the source song.

Such a system would require hours of singing from the target singers to learn how to make this kind of conversion, on a par with a singer who would need hours of practice to copy someone's singing style. The problem of having enough data to learn from is quite common in the voice conversion task and other conversion tasks such as translation between languages. The most straight forward data to learn from is *parallel*, when, in the context of singing, a singer **A** and a singer **B** sing the same songs. Meaning in the data we have separate recordings from both singers performing one or more parallel songs. It can be more than two singers but the main constraint is two have them singing the same songs. Using this sort of data will allow us to convert between singers in the dataset e.g. from the singer **A** to the singer **B** or vice versa. Furthermore, such data help to achieve the best results in the voice conversion between predefined singers because it has concrete examples of how singers sing the same songs, however, this is an expensive and hard to collect data. Another option for data is *non-parallel* when singers sing different songs and there is no direct mapping such as a singer **A** and a singer **B** sings a song **S**. Using non-parallel data for the task of voice conversion is more complicated because a system would need to learn how to convert without examples. This type of data is easier to acquire albeit until recent advances in technologies it was not possible to utilize it – With Deep Learning[1] that allows us to discover patterns and correlate voice features between two different singers, the *non-parallel* voice conversion becomes feasible.

Selecting the type of data depends on the final goal of Singing Voice Conversion and the methods that are going to be used. Unfortunately, there is not much publicly

available data with singing voice recordings in general, and for Deep Learning(DL) it is better to have as much data as possible. Hence, a preferable type of data for Singing Voice Conversion using DL is non-parallel.

1.2 Objectives

To better explain the objectives of this thesis we need to define possible expectations from the Singing Voice Conversion. When we perceive a singing voice, to identify the singer we listen to these two aspects:

- Timbre
 - Unique characteristics of the vocal cords.
 - Vocal techniques. E.g. opera, folk, or pop.
- Expression
 - Unintentional micro deviations from score.
 - Intentional deviations like vibrato.
 - Phrasing, deliberate larger deviations in timing and pitch from a music score.

Additionally, in some cases, when the singer is the author of the lyrics, people might expect a specific choice of words and style of writing, including concrete topics to write about. This aspect is out of the scope of this work because is not related to the audio directly.

Taking into account the aspects of the singer identity mentioned above, we can assume that a complete Singing Voice Conversion should be performed transforming all these aspects. I.e. if we convert a singer **A** to a singer **B**, the *timbre* and *expression* of the resulting voice should be perceived as of the singer **B**. But this might be not a strict and the only condition for a working SVC – perhaps using not all the identity’s components is enough to change the voice to sound like the target

singer. **The objective of this thesis** is to investigate how *converting only the timbre* part changes the perception of the result to be as of the target singer. The hypothesis is that the timbre is the most important in the perception of voice and thus converting only the timbre is sufficient for the task of Singing Voice Conversion.

Another objective is to make a system that can convert the voice of *any* singer to the voice of *anyone* given only the audio and no changes in the system – a Zero-Shot Singing Voice Conversion. The motivation is to create a new experience for music listeners. With such a system that can perform a zero-shot voice conversion, an artist could write a song and create a website for it where everyone could record their voices and the system would generate the song with the voices of the website users. Such a website would provide a new way of distributing deeply personalized music – a unique song for every listener, whereas, traditionally, a musician releases one version of a song to all the listeners. It is important to build this website with a system that can perform a zero-shot voice conversion because it would not require extra time to change the system for converting any visitor’s voice. Moreover, in the time of the Deepfakes, it is highly encouraging to think about the privacy of the users and try not to store or use users’ data – their voice in this case. Using zero-shot conversion we would need their voices only for the conversion part, and the result of the conversion along with the audio they get will be deleted when they leave the website.

1.3 Structure of the Report

In the next chapter we exposure existing methods for speech and singing voice conversion. In the Methods chapter, we talk in more detail how our system work and what has been done, including what data we use for training. The Results chapter provides an objective and subjective analysis of the results we obtain from different experiments. Lastly, the Conclusions chapter gives a short overview of the future steps and the results we achieved.

Chapter 2

Deep Learning for Singing Voice Conversion

2.1 Introduction

Both singing and speech types of a voice include information about: language content, timbre, pitch, and rhythm[2]. The main type of information is the *language content* which is a sung or spoken text. The unique characteristics of a voice are conveyed through the *timbre*. The functions of *pitch* and *rhythm* differ in speech and singing. For speech, it is called *prosody* and serves as the main role in expressing the emotions of the speaker. For the singing, it is usually named as a *melody* and dictated by a musical score rather than the preferences of the singer.

The aim of speech VC is to preserve the language content of the source speaker and to transform the source timbre such it sounds like the timbre of the target speaker. Usually, during the speech VC, the prosody part of the source is transformed as well. That makes speech VC fundamentally different from singing VC, where the melody and language content should be kept of the source singer and conversion takes place mostly for the timbre. If one would try to use the VC system for singing voice conversion the result most likely will be an out of tune singing-like sound with artifacts in pitch and text. However, even though singers supposed

to follow a melody, the final F0 trajectory is an important part of the singer’s expressivity[3], and will not be the same for two singers due to the reasons such as personal interpretations of a musical score which leads to slight deviations in pitch, physical characteristics of the vocal cords, unique expression techniques that singers develop to build their singing styles. This difference in the final pitch contour across any singers implies that if the goal of the conversion is to make the source singer sound exactly like the target singer, then the system should also transform the pitch contour information. In this work, we focus on the singing voice conversion applied to the timbre part of the source voice, keeping the expressive part as in the source. Despite this simplification of the task, we believe this approach is still useful for practical and creative voice conversion applications.

In general, any type of voice conversion system is based on but not limited to research in voice cloning. The task of voice cloning consists of learning the features of a speaker’s voice identity and performing text-to-speech synthesis on any text using these features. Until recent days voice synthesizers were based on concatenative methods [4] but with advances in generative models using Deep Learning these methods are not state of the art anymore. Deep learning(DL) is a technology of many uses, that have been applied to many research questions and topics. Voice analysis, processing, and synthesis are no exception. For instance, vocal pitch extraction[5], singing processing[6], and singing synthesis[7]. These and many more works that use Deep Neural Networks demonstrate superior performance compared to previous statistical or domain-knowledge-based approaches. Our work employs AutoVC[8] architecture, a recent state of the art speech VC system that uses DL to perform speech voice conversion.

Ideally, one would want a system that converts any voice to anyone’s voice given only their audio, and without changes in the system. That system would perform a zero-shot voice conversion which is not yet well studied in comparison to converting voices between speakers that the system used in the training phase. The AutoVC model that we use, is capable of zero-shot speech VC but can not be used directly on singing voice because of the differences between speech VC and singing VC mentioned at

the beginning of this chapter. Zero-shot singing voice conversion has a particular interest in us because it has never been studied before and thus makes this work a valuable contribution to the field of singing VC. AutoVC can perform zero-shot VC because it uses neural networks to generate unique low-dimensional vectors – embeddings – that serve the role of speaker labels in their system. That means, given a set of recordings of the same speaker it will generate very similar to each other embeddings. Because of the uniqueness of the embeddings per speaker, they are often used in speaker verification systems[9]. The focal point of our research is to compare different algorithms for generating these embeddings and to see how they affect the quality of the singing VC in general and more specifically zero-shot conversion.

2.2 Voice Conversion Algorithms

A typical voice conversion system consists of the training phase and the conversion phase. Figure 1 demonstrates an overview of these phases. First, the system needs to be trained, during this phase a conversion model is learning to map the source features to the target features. The training part usually takes days, depending on how much data is used and the architecture of the conversion model. When the training is done we can proceed to the conversion phase, where a new source speech is analyzed to get the features to convert. Then, the source features are converted with the trained model into the target features, which are finally used to synthesize the converted speech in the target speaker’s voice. The conversion phase comparatively to the training phase happens in real-time.

Speech analysis

The first and the last steps are *Speech analysis* and *Speech synthesis*. They are directly related to each other because the latter should synthesize speech based on the outputs from the analysis step. In many cases, for speech analysis and synthesis, VC systems often use external solutions such as WORLD[10] that utilize statistical models and domain knowledge or WaveNet[11] which is Neural Vocoder.

Figure 1: A general scheme of a voice conversion system.

Feature extraction

During the feature extraction stage, the system should extract features from the input signal that are relevant to the task of voice conversion. Meaning, these features should represent the acoustic properties of speech. Because a speech signal is non-stationary the processing happens frame-wise. One frame is a short signal usually of 10-30 msec which is considered to be stationary due to its short nature. Additionally, these frames overlap with each other to process most of the possible variations. From these frames, we extract the features then.

Conversion model training

Depends on the model and the architecture of the conversion system, as well as on data used during the training. The point is that extracted features are used to train an algorithm that is capable of generating similar features that in the consequence will be used to synthesize the converted voice.

Conversion

After the conversion model is trained, the system can take any speech recording as the source speaker input. The next steps of the conversion phase are the same as during the training: first, it analyses the input speech; then it extracts features of the source speaker. With extracted features, it uses the trained model to map these features to the target speaker. In the system displayed in Figure 1 the target can be selected only among those speakers that were used during the training phase. We discuss later in this section what are the types of VC systems exist and how they differ. Finally, then the conversion model produces the target features the last step is to use them to synthesize speech.

2.2.1 VC System Types

VC methods can be categorized by (i) alignment of data that was used during the training phase, (ii) capacity of voice conversion to and from an arbitrary speaker from the dataset, and (iii) if they can do the zero-shot conversion. In the first category,

if the source and target speakers read the same sentences it is called parallel data, otherwise non-parallel data. In the second category, one-to-one voice conversion is when it can be done only from one speaker to another one, but if the algorithm can generalize and perform voice conversion from any speaker to any speaker in the dataset it is called one-to-many or many-to-many. Last but not least category is the most challenging, where the conversion happens between unseen speakers that are outside of the dataset. In most cases, these categories arise from differences in the data but we concentrate on these three because our goal is *non-parallel many-to-many zero-shot singing voice conversion* system.

Previously, most of the VC systems were limited to parallel data only, utilizing vector quantization for mapping between source and target features with the help of the Gaussian mixture model(GMM)[12]. However, there is a way to employ non-parallel data with GMM which is to use maximum-likelihood constrained adaptation method[13]. On the other hand, the current state of the art VC systems use different than GMM methods and can train a model using non-parallel data with the help of Deep Learning. Many methods based on generative adversarial networks (GANs)[14] and autoencoders have been proposed to address the Speech Voice Conversion task. Among the methods that use GANs[15, 16], different variations of using a cycle consistency loss[17] were introduced: [18, 19, 20]. Additionally, StarGAN[21] adaptations were made for Voice Conversion: [22, 23]. On the side of autoencoder-based solutions, there are AutoVC[8], VQVC+[24], an extension[25] of AutoVC that makes it more consistent with F0, and the latest advancement[2] of AutoVC that allows it to decompose the source to timbre, pitch, and rhythm information making it capable of converting the voices in these domains separately or mixed.

2.2.2 AutoVC

Recently, AutoVC[8], a conditional autoencoder (CAEs) based method achieved state-of-the-art results by disentangling the speaker identity and speech content using information-constraining bottlenecks, and it achieves zero-shot conversion by

Figure 2: AutoVC framework. X represents voice audio and Z and U correspond to the content such as language and speaker identity such as timbre respectively. $Es(\cdot)$ is a pre-trained Speaker Encoder while $Ec(\cdot)$ is the Content Encoder and $D(\cdot, \cdot)$ is the Decoder. (a) Depicts the inference where the source speaker is the input to the Content Encoder and the target is fed to the Speaker Encoder (b) Represents the training stage where the same speaker but different utterances go to the Speaker Encoder and Content Encoder to self reconstruct itself. This figure extracted from AutoVC paper[8]

swapping in a different speaker’s identity embedding to synthesize a new voice. Among the mentioned above papers, Qian’s AutoVC[8] proposes a simple architecture and able to perform zero-shot VC and thus makes it a great candidate to adjust for Singing VC task. As seen in Figure 2 AutoVC comprises of three modules: (i) a content encoder that produces a content embedding from speech, (ii) a speaker encoder that produces a speaker embedding from speech, and (iii) a decoder that produces speech from content and speaker embeddings. In the original AutoVC model, their speaker encoder was pre-trained on the combination of VoxCeleb1[26] and Librispeech[27] corpora using mel-spectrograms as input and utilizing GE2E loss[9] that helps to maximize the embedding similarity between different samples of the same speaker, and minimize the similarity among different speakers.

The Speaker Encoder

The speaker encoder is supposed to encode different utterances of the same speaker equally while for different speakers it should produce different embeddings. Because the task of AutoVC is zero-shot conversion they cannot use conventional one-hot en-

Figure 3: AutoVC architecture. (a) Depicts Content Encoder. The $E_s(\cdot)$ is the same as (b). (b) The architecture of the Speaker Encoder. (c) The architecture of the Decoder. (d) Speech synthesizer. (e) and (f) show how the bottleneck is working with an example of a down-sampling factor of 3. This figure extracted from AutoVC paper[8]

coding for speaker identities, therefore they built an embedding that is generalizable to unseen speakers which were influenced by GE2E loss.

The Content Encoder

The goal of the content encoder is to disentangle the speaker’s identity from the language content. It achieves this with the help of the information-constraining bottleneck which is downsampling the input by the factor of 32.

The Decoder

The decoder takes as input the downsampled encoding from the content encoder and upsamples it back to the original input size while adding the speaker identity based on the speaker embedding provided as the input to the decoder.

2.3 Singing Voice Conversion Algorithms

Taking into account most of the methods for Singing VC have been adapted from Speech VC we can observe similar major groups: autoencoder and GANs based architectures. The latter has a few examples, for instance, Sisman uses limited parallel data to train a GAN model[28] while Wu proposed a method[18] for singing style

transfer without paired data by combining CycleGAN with the training strategy of BEGAN. More works utilize autoencoder pattern: Nachmani introduces an unsupervised method with non-parallel data[29] and Deng extends Nachmani’s work in their PitchNet[30] model. Additionally, Luo explores how to disentangle representations of singer and vocal technique[31]. Most of these works are based on research in the speech voice conversion systems such as GAN-based [16, 32, 33] or CVE-based [8, 34, 35] models.

2.3.1 Unsupervised Singing Voice Conversion

Similarly to AutoVC, Unsupervised Singing Voice Conversion(USVC)[29] uses a content encoder and a singer decoder which is compared to AutoVC is conditioned on a one-hot encoding of the target singer. During the training stage they mixup and back-translation techniques which divide the training into two stages: In the first stage, a self-reconstruction of each singer separately. In the second, they generate synthetic singers by mixing vocal characteristics of two singers from the training data and converted them to existing singers and then use the same self-reconstruction loss as in the first stage. Finally, to make sure that the encoder disentangles the speaker’s information from the language content they utilize a domain confusion loss[36]. One problem with this model is that because there is no conditioning on the pitch information from the source it fails consistently to maintain the original melody during the conversion.

2.3.2 PitchNet

This model is a continuation of the USVC model which tries to resolve an obvious problem with USVC – it does not follow the source melody well. To do that they extract pitch information from the source audio and condition the decoder on it. Additionally to that, to make sure that the encoder not only removes the speaker information but the pitch content, they add a pitch regression network that helps to disentangle pitch information from the latent space of the encoder. They also use as in USVC back-translation and mixup techniques during the training phase.

Figure 4: USVC framework. E represents the speaker encoder, C is a model that helps to disentangle speaker content from the encoder output. D is a conditional decoder that takes as input the encoded language content and the speaker embedding which is stored in a table. This figure extracted from USVC paper[29]

Figure 5: PitchNet architecture. It mostly repeats the USVC approach except for additional pitch analysis and conditioning of the decoder with the extracted pitch from the source audio. Also, they make sure that encoder encodes only the language content by adding a pitch regression network that helps to disentangle pitch information from the encoder output. This figure is taken from PitchNet paper[30]

Chapter 3

Methods

Because the main goal of this work is to achieve zero-shot conversion we choose to adapt zero-shot capable AutoVC model to the case of the singing voice. The main reason why the original AutoVC architecture is not suitable for singing voice is that it does not take into account pitch-related information during the training and conversion stages. While pitch, as we explained in the previous chapter, is a crucial part of the singing voice.

Another constraints are computational power and the speed of conversion – AutoVC uses WaveNet vocoder which is computationally expensive to train and it is slow in generation audio because it utilizes an auto-regressive architecture. Which means WaveNet has to predict audio sample by sample. To overcome these two major blocks of the missing pitch information and WaveNet vocoder, we decided to use the WORLD vocoder that can do both: disentangle pitch information from the timbre and do a real-time inference. Plus, the WORLD does not need the training phase.

WORLD is a statistical method based on CheapTrick[37], DIO[38], and PLATINUM[39] for estimating spectral envelope, F0 contour, and aperiodic signal respectively. This analysis is then used in the synthesis algorithm which comprises calculating the vocal cord vibration with the convolution of the minimum phase response and excitation signal extracted from the waveform, F0, and spectral envelope. Our adapted ver-

Figure 6: WORLD framework. This figure extracted from WORLD paper[10].

Figure 7: WORLD synthesis framework. This figure extracted from WORLD paper[10]

sion of AutoVC takes as input the spectral envelope part of the extracted WORLD features because it is supposed to convey the timbre and language information only. This should help the encoder part of AutoVC to disentangle the singer content from the language information better than in the case of using mel-spectrograms as input. That should be true because mel-spectrograms have all information together and the encoder needs to separate timbre, pitch, language, and other content. Additionally, using the WORLD helps to slightly reduce the computation cost because the input size is smaller than the original 80 samples per mel-spectrogram. The size of WORLD features is 1025 but after a dimension reduction proposed in [7] the final size is 66 and if we remove the pitch and aperiodicity parts it will be 64 only.

Figure 8 depicts all the changes made to the original AutoVC architecture. Apart from using WORLD for udio analysis and synthesis, we changed the bottleneck size. Instead of the original 8, we empirically came to the size of 16. When we use 8 the system produces noticeably degraded audio quality compared to the results of the original AutoVC model. One explanation for that problem is the smaller size

Figure 8: Adapted to singing voice AutoVC architecture. This figure extracted from AutoVC paper[8] and modified.

of the input: smaller size could mean that the bigger part of it has the timbre and language content information. Another theory is that WORLD features are cleaner in terms of the content: as discussed at the beginning of the chapter - we use only the spectral envelope part of the WORLD features so the bottleneck does not to be smaller to remove pitch and other irrelevant information. Thus, having more specific for the task features could allow us to have a bigger bottleneck.

3.1 Speaker/Singer Embedding

The last biggest change to the AutoVC system is to use different speaker embeddings. The authors of AutoVC trained a speaker encoder with GE2E loss on VoxCeleb1 and LibriSpeech datasets with the total number of speakers equal to 3549. In our case, we use a pre-trained speaker encoder(Resemblyzer)¹ which is also based on GE2E loss but trained with more data and has closer results to the original GE2E paper. Resemblyzer used Librispeech, VoxCeleb1, and VoxCeleb2[40] datasets with total of 8.4k speakers. Both speaker encoders used datasets that contain only speech recordings, and this is, arguably, a potential reason why these speaker encoders should not be used in the context of the singing voice. However, for the sake of experiments we

¹<https://github.com/resemble-ai/Resemblyzer>

want to find out if a speaker encoder trained on speech is generalizable enough for the singing voice.

To answer that question we need to compare the results of GE2E speaker embeddings with other embeddings trained on the singing voice. A fair comparison would require another speaker encoder with the same GE2E architecture but trained on the singing voice. Unfortunately, there are no publicly available datasets with as many as 3 or 8 thousand singers, and training on less data does not set equal conditions. Nevertheless, we can use another model that was built for singer identification and can generate singer embeddings – Joint Embeddings(JE)[41]. Even though it was also trained with fewer data – 1000 singers – we can compare the results obtained with this model and GE2E because it is a comparison of two different methods rather than the same method with different sizes of data. JE presented the state of the art results in the task of singer identification which would be equivalent to GE2E that performs state of the art in speaker identification.

Similarly to the WORLD features, we pre-compute embeddings and reuse in different experiments. In the case of JE, we use implementation² open-sourced by its authors, along with the pre-trained models. GE2E solution is also external and open-sourced by the authors of [?]. Luckily enough, the embeddings dimensions are the same for both GE2E and JE models. It reduces the complexity of supporting and experimenting with different conversion models because we don't need to have a separate version of architecture that works with a particular embedding dimension.

GE2E which is trained with speech data takes as input 1.6 seconds of audio converted to 40-channels log-mel spectrograms with window width and step size of 23 ms and 10 ms respectively. Then, this model outputs a vector of 256 elements which is the L2-normalized hidden state of the last layer. JE, in its turn, takes as input 3-second long audio of at least 70% singing voice frames converted into a 128 bins mel-spectrogram calculated with 46ms window width and 23 ms step. The output is also the hidden state of the last convolutional layer that comprises of 256 elements.

²<https://github.com/kyungyunlee/mono2mixed-singer>

There are differences in the input sizes and analysis between these speaker embedding models which leads to different data pre-processing steps. To make sure both algorithms perform as they expected we use pre-processing steps provided by the authors of the algorithms. However, one step is common for all – voice activity segmentation. This step is taken from Resemblyzer and helps to remove silent regions from the input audio. Another big difference between GE2E and JE pre-processing steps is the sampling rate of audio samples. GE2E from Resemblyzer resamples audio to be 16kHz, whereas JE resamples to 22kHz. Sampling rate affects the quality of the embeddings but not necessarily a higher sampling rate means better embeddings. After experiments with 44kHz audio, we did not find big improvements in the quality, and in some cases, it leads to degrading the separation between embeddings. To keep the systems as close to their original pre-processing flows we use 16kHz and 22kHz for GE2E and JE models accordingly.

AutoVC uses GE2E embeddings for speaker encoding to achieve zero-shot conversion. Those embeddings were trained and made for speech and thus might be not the best choice for the singing voice. We try other embeddings that were trained on singing voice and compare with the results that we achieve using GE2E embeddings.

3.2 Datasets

Having defined data analysis and pre-processing steps we could finalize data flow for our system. First, we extract voice-only segments from the input audio. Then, from each segment, we extract WORLD features and save them as HDF5 files for each segment separately. The embeddings calculation, on the other hand, happens on the segments accumulated into one audio so it contains only voice and no long silences. Which then is saved as NumPy array file. So from one input audio file, we have many hdf5 files representing voice segments and only one NumPy array file that represent singer embeddings. These files are then reused during the training and inference stages. This flow is depicted in Figure 9 and every audio sample from the datasets goes through it.

Figure 9: Data pre-processing

Dataset	Language	Unprocessed Tracks
Isophonics[42]	Chinese\English\More	Yes
MTG-QBH[43]	English	Yes
iKala[44]	Chinese	Yes
Analysis of Intonation Trajectories in Solo Singing[45]	English	Yes
NUS [46]	English	Yes
TONAS[47]	Spanish	Yes
SING/DAMP ³	Different	Yes
ccMixer[48]	English	Some
RWC Music Database[49]	Japanese\English	Yes
DALI[50]	English	No
VocalSet[51]	Vowels	Yes
JVS-MuSiC [52]	Japanese	Yes
Kiritan singing ⁴	Japanese	Yes
MUSDB18[53]	English	No

Table 1: Singing voice datasets we found and considered for our research.

In Table 1 we present the list of datasets from our research on what data is available for the singing voice. This is a not complete list and may have some outdated data but we believe one might find them useful anyway. The DAMP dataset would be a great collection to use in our task because it has thousands of singers but most of the recordings are noisy and mixed with music and background sounds. The DALI and MusDB18 each have around 100+ singers to collect but the audio is processed with effects that can affect the conversion quality. The VocalSet has promising 10 hours of recordings from 20 speakers but all of them just vowels, not real songs. The rest has either a small number of singers or different from the English language which might be problematic if we mix datasets.

The final number of training examples in our experiments varies depending on what datasets are being used. Overall, we have selected NUS, JVS, and proprietary (PRP) datasets but we use different combinations of them across our experiments. NUS contains recordings of the spoken and sung lyrics of 48 English songs by 12 subjects of 6 males and 6 females. JVS is 100 native Japanese professional speakers of 49 males and 51 females each singing 2 songs in Japanese. PRP comprises of 46 professional singers performing 204 songs in English.

³<https://ccrma.stanford.edu/damp/>

⁴https://github.com/mmorise/kiritan_singing

3.3 Experiments

The main experiments that we undertake use different datasets for us to analyze the effect of smaller and bigger sizes of data on the conversion quality. Both USVC and PitchNet use the NUS dataset only and thus for a fair comparison we need to constraint some of our experiments to NUS only as well. However, taking into account that NUS is a small dataset and USVC with PitchNet did not have the task of zero-shot voice conversion which ideally requires more data we need to expand our experiments with PRP and possibly JVS datasets. For the task of zero-shot conversion, we need as many different singers as possible to train the models generalizable to different timbres. A potential problem with using JVS for that is mixing languages, even though, in theory, it should not affect the conversion quality because our target is the timbre rather than language and the system should just learn how to synthesize additional 100 timbres from JVS. Ultimately, we experiment with each dataset separately and all possible permutations lie NUS and JVS, or JVS and PRP. This way we can assess the effect of the datasets on the quality of conversion.

Apart from the effect of different datasets during the training, we want to investigate the performance of AutoVC architecture without the zero-shot capacity. For instance, in one experiment we replace speaker embeddings with one-hot labels that represent unique singer number the dataset. This is our base model that demonstrates the quality of the conversion purely from the architectural point of view. We will call it AVC-OH throughout the document. The models that use GE2E and JE embeddings are called AVC-GE2E and AVC-JE respectively. Different variations with datasets we call AVC-OH-NUS, AVC-JE-NUS-PRP, etc.

The last experiment we want to explore is to adapt the VQVC+ model to use WORLD features and synthesize the results with WORLD as well. VQVC+ is also capable of zero-shot voice conversion but utilizes essentially different architecture compared to AutoVC. VQVC+ does not need external speaker embeddings as it learns them by itself during the training stage. Because of that the only change we need to make to it is to use WORLD analysis and synthesis. That would also make

the audio quality equal across all of our experiments. We call the adapted to the WORLD version of VQVC+ as VQVC-W.

Finally, before proceeding to the training stage of the models we extract WORLD features from the resampled to 32kHz audio samples of all available datasets. As well as generating GE2E and JE embeddings from 16kHz and 22kHz resampled audio samples. During the training stage, AutoVC-based models are trained for 2500 epochs on Titan X GPU which takes around a day to complete. While VQVC-W is trained only for 800 epochs and it takes around 3 days to finish the training because this model has to learn its speaker encoder for singer embeddings, while AutoVC uses pre-computed embeddings.

Before we begin training with pre-processed data we also want to analyze how well our speaker and singer encoders work in the task of singer classification. For that, we generate GE2E and JE embeddings for the singing part of the NUS dataset which results in 48 embeddings from 12 subjects and 4 songs per each. Next, we want to compare the embeddings of one song with another to see how close they are to each other. To do so we compute the cosine similarity between the embeddings and plot it as a confusion matrix as well as a histogram. We repeat the steps once more but not only for comparing between two songs but computing a mean of all the embeddings per singer. Taking into account that in NUS there are only 4 songs per singer and we would need to split them in a half to compare the same singer it results in a comparison between only 2 songs per singer. Thus the difference between the results of these two tests is not big.

Chapter 4

Results

Our main model to compare with is USVC. At the moment of writing this thesis, the authors of another comparable model – PitchNet – did not respond to our request to use their examples of conversions available on their website. And there is no complete and open-sourced implementation of PitchNet so we could not generate our examples. Additionally, we did not have time to implement PitchNet nor USVC by ourselves. For those who want to compare our results with PitchNet, we suggest visiting their webpage¹ along with ours². All the following analysis and evaluation is made with NUS dataset because it has been used for the USVC model.

4.1 Evaluation

4.1.1 Embeddings analysis

Most of the systems that generate audio are difficult to evaluate objectively because existing methods for the objective evaluation are not always consistent with human perception. However, there are some attempts to automate the subjective evaluation of audio generating systems, in particular, MosNet[54] tries to predict human ratings of converted speech. MosNet was built for evaluation speech conversion so it does not cover our case of the singing voice.

¹<https://tencent-ailab.github.io/pitch-net/>

²<https://apisov.github.io/zs-svc/>

Figure 10: GE2E and JE embeddings similarity with NUS sing data. On the left side is GE2E and on the left is JE. The top row corresponds to the comparison between one song per singer while the bottom row compares between the mean of 2 songs per singer.

The idea behind our objective evaluation of the system relies on the effectiveness of speaker embeddings. As we mentioned in the previous chapter, we tested GE2E and JE embeddings on the task of singer identification and expanded it to the speech data of the NUS dataset to see how well they perform on speech, singing, and both types of voice. In Figure 10 we can see that JE and GE2E have similar performance in terms of identifying a singer but it is interesting to see how different the embeddings of other singers. In the case of GE2E, the embeddings of the same singer and different singers are close to each other, however, the mean result for different singers is still smaller than from the same singer. JE on the other hand spreads the embeddings of the different singers from opposite to similar and makes the margin between the same singer and different singers bigger than in GE2E. This shows us that JE performs better in separating embeddings from different singers in the case of the singing voice. It also confirms our hypothesis that a speaker encoder trained on large enough speech data can be used as well for the singing voice.

Figure 11: GE2E and JE embeddings similarity with NUS speech data. On the left side is GE2E and on the left is JE. The top row corresponds to the comparison between one utterance per speaker while the bottom row compares between the mean of 2 utterances per speaker.

To verify if the generalization is reversible we want to analyze the embeddings on the speech data from NUS. In Figure 11 we observe that the results are quite similar to the case of the singing data which proves that a singer encoder could be used for speaker identification. This Figure also shows that GE2E outperforms JE in identifying the same speaker which is logical considering it was trained on a large dataset of speech data. GE2E also has better embeddings separation than in the case of the singing data but still not as large as in the JE case.

The final test is to assess how GE2E and JE behave with mixed data of singing and speech data to see if that would affect the performance. In Figure 12 the first row duplicates the results from the singing data because it used one song per person, however, the second row shows the result of mixing the singing and speech data which gives us 4 recordings per person. The results as expected are worse than with the clean data because singing voice and speech voice of the same person can be very different and that would be even a hard task for a human. It might be even

Figure 12: GE2E and JE embeddings similarity with NUS speech and singing data combined. The top row corresponds to the comparison between one song per speaker while the bottom row compares between the mean of 2 utterances and 2 songs per speaker.

harder for a human because we cannot hear subtle patterns in the timbre that can be shared across singing and speech data. Not surprisingly GE2E classifies better because it had more data to learn from the deep features of the human voice that can be later found in the singing and speech voices. JE even if performs worse than GE2E is still capable of differentiating the same singer from different singers taking the mean values of the results. But in general, both models are not suitable for use with the mixed data.

To explore more how the chosen embeddings separate different singers and group the same singer we project the embeddings in a two-dimensional space with UMAP[55]. We project the embeddings for different cases as we did for the similarity – singing only data, speech, and mix of speech and singing voices. In the case of separates plots of speech and singing voices, we see two groups in all of them which correspond to the gender of the singers. Nevertheless, within those gender groups, it is still possible to find local groups of the same singers. GE2E embeddings perform best in the case

Figure 13: UMAP projections of GE2E and JE embeddings from 4 songs or 4 utterances per person. On the left side, there are two separate plots for GE2E embeddings from speech and singing voices. The two plots on the right represent JE embeddings.

Figure 14: UMAP projections of GE2E and JE embeddings for 8 recordings of speech and voice per person. The left plot depicts GE2E embeddings and the right one is JE embeddings.

of speech voice while JE does not show a great superiority over GE2E in the case of the singing voice. Both GE2E and JE group singers better in the case of speech due to the nature of speech voice – it has fewer variations and the timbre tends to be similar across the whole recording. While singing voice could be changing in pitch and rhythm. An interesting observation is coming from the plots of the mixed data: in Figure 13 GE2E groups singing and speech data separately but in some cases close to each other in the space and others far apart. One explanation could be that some singing styles can be very different from the average speech voice while the other singing styles can be closer to speech. That explains why one singer has embeddings of its speech and singing closer to each other while the other singers can have them far apart. To some extent, contradicting the results of the embeddings similarity, in Figure 14 JE groups the mixed data better because there are two distinct blobs of embeddings but still separated by gender as in the case of separate speech or singing data. Although, those two blobs have a bigger surface compared to the separate voices and that might explain why JE cannot perform better than GE2E in the case of the mixed data. In the end, these projections show that both embeddings are not very suitable for the mixed data as it was also showed with the similarity matrices.

To conclude the embeddings analysis, GE2E seems to be more effective in both cases – speech and singing voices – which probably can be explained with more data used during the training of the model we used in the analysis. Nonetheless, JE shows some minimal capacity for being general enough for speech and singing voice applications and it might be improved with more data and perhaps even mixed data.

4.1.2 Objective evaluation

After we verified that GE2E and JE embeddings work with the NUS dataset we want to assess the quality of the voice conversion of some of the models we trained. All the next analysis was made with the models that were trained on NUS and PRP datasets because we want to see what is the maximum performance we could get from the different architectures and embeddings in use. We analyze AutoVC-based

models with GE2E and JE embeddings along with AutoVC with one-hot labels.

The evaluation comprises of 3 steps: (i) convert pairs from NUS singers. The first singer gets converted to the second, second is converted to the third one, and so on until the last is converted with the first one. (ii) Generate GE2E and JE embeddings for the converted examples as well as for the target examples of converted voices. (iii) Plot embeddings similarity for one example from a singer and the mean of all conversion examples.

In the Methods chapter, we said that we generate WORLD features after segmenting songs into shorted audios that consist only from the voice to remove silences and make the training examples shorted. We randomly select for each singer 4 fragments with the duration from 4 to 6 seconds and then convert between the pairs of the singers as described in the evaluation step 1. Whenever we convert between two singers we also synthesize the source and target singers to have the target voice examples. In the end, every singer has 4 examples of the voice conversion to its timbre as well as 4 examples of the original samples of it synthesized with WORLD. All the examples are synthesized with WORLD and thus the audio quality will be the same. To make the comparison fairer we use the same 4 examples of the original voices across all the experiments with different models so the embeddings of the original voices will be the same all the time.

To summarise, each model generates 48 examples of conversions where every singer will have 4 examples. From one of the conversion executions, we will select 48 examples of the original voices and will be comparing them to 48 conversion examples from different models.

We first start from the base model results to establish what is our goal. In Figure 15 we can see how the quality of the similarity deteriorated compared to the embeddings analysis in the previous subsection. One reason is that we use much shorter examples to generate embeddings. In the analysis, we used the whole songs which would be 3-4 minutes on average while in the evaluation the examples are 4-6 seconds long. Additionally, the quality of the synthesized converted voice should have some

Figure 15: GE2E embeddings similarity of the conversions with the AVC-OH-NUS-PRP.

Figure 16: JE embeddings similarity of the conversions with the AVC-OH-NUS-PRP.

effect as well. However, in contrast to the embeddings analysis, we can see how the similarity differs for the case of comparison between one example of around 5 seconds and the mean of 4 examples of 5 seconds – the more examples the bigger similarity. Despite that the mean of the predicted values from the embeddings analysis and the objective evaluation are similar. The matrix similarity depicts more clear that the embeddings are less similar to each other in the case of the objective evaluation. The situation with JE embeddings in Figure 16 is correlated with the embeddings analysis – the similarity is worse than GE2E. However, due to the nature of JE embeddings that better separates embeddings from each other, there is a more visible diagonal between the converted and original voices. Although, the median of the predicted values is smaller than in GE2E which proves that GE2E is better for classification even of the converted voices.

Going forward to AutoVC model that use GE2E embeddings we see in Figure 17 a slightly decreased accuracy compared to the base model. And in Figure 18 depicted that the quality is also less than in the base model. There are also more visible correlations between the converted and the next original singers which we try to explain later.

Figure 17: GE2E embeddings similarity of the conversions with the AVC-GE2E-NUS-PRP.

Figure 18: JE embeddings similarity of the conversions with the AVC-GE2E-NUS-PRP.

Figure 19: GE2E embeddings similarity of the conversions with the AVC-JE-NUS-PRP.

Figure 20: JE embeddings similarity of the conversions with the AVC-JE-NUS-PRP.

Finally, the last model to evaluate is the AutoVC-based model trained with JE embeddings. The results are depicted in Figures 19 and 20. The similarity continues to decrease and this is correlated with our findings during the embeddings analysis where we found that GE2E embeddings are better in the classification. This may suggest that the better embeddings at singer or speaker identification the better quality of the conversion. The last and important comment on the conversion analysis which is true for all the models but has different severity is that there is a bias to the next singer on the list. Meaning that if look at Figure 19 and similarity between MCUR-C and MPOL-O we can observe that it is higher than between MPOL-C and MPOL-O. And this can be found for some other singers especially it is visible in Figure 17 for the cases JLEE-C and JTAN-O, MPUR-C and NJAT-O, and VKOW-C and ZHIY-O. This can be explained with our decision to have ordered pairs from the list of singers – ADIZ converted to JLEE, JLEE to JTAN, VKOW to ZHIY, and so on – because the conversion results in most of the cases have more similarity to the source singer rather than the target.

In the conclusion of the objective evaluation, we could tell that AVC-OH-NUS-PRP performs the best as it was expected from the base model, however, the difference between the embeddings is not significant and GE2E is slightly outperforms JE. In Table 2 we can see the difference between the evaluations using GE2E and JE embeddings. GE2E yet again proved to be better in the classification and, potentially, because of that, the model that uses GE2E performs better during the voice conversion. Looking at these findings we could hypothesize that in the subjective evaluation the AVC-GE2E-NUS-PRP and AVC-OH-NUS-PRP models will be the best performing.

Model	GE2E	JE
AVC-OH-NUS-PRP	0.93	0.76
AVC-GE2E-NUS-PRP	0.91	0.74
AVC-JE-NUS-PRP	0.89	0.61

Table 2: The median values of comparing the same singer with converted and original voices. The GE2E column represents an analysis of the audio with GE2E embeddings, and JE column the same but with JE embeddings.

4.1.3 Subjective Evaluation

To conduct subjective tests we used BeagleJS³ framework that allows us to create browser-based listening tests and therefore can be easily distributed among participants. We deploy the website using GitHub Pages⁴ and store the results on Firebase⁵. In the listening tests, we used the same models as in the objective evaluation i.e. that were trained with NUS and PRP datasets, however, we also added the VQVC-W model to assess it subjectively as well as USVC. The comparison to USVC is not completely fair because it used only the NUS dataset during the training while our models had an additional proprietary dataset which is four times larger than NUS. We admit this difference and specifically show USVC-NUS on the comparison plots to denote that the datasets are different. The test took 15 anonymous participants with the majority of them being slightly familiar with the topic and only a few people were strongly familiar with the topic of the voice conversion. The test is divided into 8 different sections. All of them have source and target references at the top of the section and the subject will be asked to rate test items by comparing with the references based on:

- **Target Timbre Similarity:** How similar the timbre of the voice of a Test Item to the Target Timbre from the references.
- **Source Melody Matching:** Represents how close the melody of the Test Item to the melody of the Source reference.
- **Source Language Matching:** Represents how good preservation of words, elocution, and articulation, as well as intelligibility, compared to the Source
- **Audio Quality:** Depicts the overall perceptual impression of the quality of the synthesized vocals. This could take into account any possible audio impairments that the listeners may deem relevant.

³<https://github.com/HSU-ANT/beaglejs>

⁴<https://pages.github.com/>

⁵<https://firebase.google.com/>

Compared to the objective evaluation, the conversion examples for the listening tests were selected manually and were mostly influenced by the examples from USVC because we need to use the same examples as USVC has on its web page⁶. The listening tests can be roughly separated into 3 groups: (i) Five tests of Male to Male conversion compared between all 5 models(AVC-OH, AVC-GE2E, AVC-JE, VQVC-W, USVC). (ii) One test of Female to Female with 4 models(AVC-OH, AVC-GE2E, AVC-JE, VQVC-W). (iii) And two tests with zero-shot conversions of seen Female to unseen Male and unseen Male to unseen Male compared only between AVC-GE2E and AVC-JE models. Because some models are used in different groups it makes sense to assess them separately in those groups of the tests where they all present. For example, in Figure 21 depicted MOS of only AutoVC-based models that were used in Male to Male and Female to Female tests. Contradicting to our objective evaluation results, AVC-GE2E performs better than the base AVC-OH model which proves the point that objective evaluation of audio is a complex task because human audio perception has to be taken into consideration. However, there is still a correlation with the objective tests – AVC-JE performs the worst between those 3 models.

If we compare the results of the AVC-GE2E and AVC-JE only, we can use all the 8 tests including zero-shot conversions. Figure 23 shows again that AVC-GE2E performs better than AVC-JE and MOS values are not different from the previous comparison because we added only two zero-shot conversion results which means zero-shot results are not drastically worse than conversion between seen singers. Although we admit that the number of the zero-shot tests is small to make this assumption completely valid but we still demonstrate separately zero-shot conversion results in Figure 25. In our subjective opinion, the zero-shot conversion results sound of less quality in terms of timbre, language, and overall audio quality but the 15 subjects voted the language and audio quality to be similar to the seen singers conversion, and the timbre conversion is noticeably worse for GE2E embeddings and for the first and the only time JE embeddings outperforms GE2E in the task of zero-shot voice conversion.

⁶https://enk100.github.io/Unsupervised_singing_voice_conversion/

Figure 21: MOS of the conversion results from the AVC-GE2E, AVC-JE, and AVC-OH models.

Figure 22: MOS of the conversion results from the USVC-NUS, AVC-OH models.

Figure 23: MOS of the conversion results from the AVC-GE2E, AVC-JE models.

Figure 24: MOS of the conversion results from the AVC-GE2E, AVC-JE, VQVC-W models.

Figure 25: MOS of the zero-shot conversion results from the AVC-GE2E, AVC-JE models.

Another model that we want to evaluate but skipped in the objective tests is VQVC-W. This model was adapted in the last minutes of this thesis so we had not enough time to verify that everything is correct. Especially after hearing the initial results from this model where we found some kind of glitches in the audio. We believe the glitches were due to the quantized nature of the embeddings used in VCVQ+. While these work well for speech signals, which involve shorter (in duration) and consistent (in formant structure) phonemes, the phoneme duration and formant structures in singing voice are variant over time and the quantized embeddings might not fully capture these subtle variations, leading to glitches. Despite the glitches, we decided to use this model in the subjective tests to confirm that the quality is worse than most of our other results. In Figure 24 we compare other AVC embeddings models with VQVC-W and the results of VQVC-W are in the case of comparing to AVC-GE2E as twice as worse.

Last but not least, the USVC model was compared only to AVC-OH because they both use one-hot labels to encode the singers. As was mentioned before this is not a totally fair comparison due to different datasets used during the training stage of these models. Our listening tests already had many tests and it was taking around 15-30 minutes and longer for people who are not very familiar with the topic so we wanted to sacrifice having more comparisons between proper models to the chance of having enough people to complete the listening tests. In Figure 22 there is an expected difference between the results for Melody Matching – USVC is not capable of strictly following the melody of the source singer because the pitch information is not used anywhere separately in the architecture of this model. While in the case of AVC models we extract the melody from the source and use it to synthesize the converted voice with the target timbre. That’s why in the ideal case all the AVC models should have had similar results for the Melody Matching but different songs have different melody complexity and the subjects could vary in their ability to recognize the melody properly. There is also a chance that WORLD analysis fails from time to time but in our experiments, we did not hear any mistakes with the pitch analysis. Regardless of the worse Melody Matching of USVC-NUS it still performs better than AVC-OH-NUS-PRP in terms of Timbre Similarity and

Overall Audio Quality. However, the Language Content preservation is better in AVC-OH-NUS-PRP which can be explained with having more data to train on and WORLD features being better in separating language content from the rest of the voice information.

To conclude the subjective analysis, we calculate the mean values of the different test groups but the same model and create a table to compare the results from all the five models that were included in the listening tests. In Table 3 we can notice that on average AVC-GE2E-NUS-PRP performs better in all characteristics and just slightly outperforms USVC-W-NUS in terms of the Timbre conversion which is an interesting observation considering our model had more data to train on. Perhaps, the timbre conversion quality does not depend that much on the data how on the architectural choices of the model. Although, both USVC and AVC use a similar idea with auto-encoder and there is no big difference in that. The results of the subjective analysis are somewhat correlated with the objective analysis with the only difference that AVC-GE2E was evaluated better than AVC-OH on contrary to the objective tests.

Model	Timbre	Melody	Language	Audio
AVC-OH-NUS-PRP	42.33	57.55	58.75	34.33
AVC-GE2E-NUS-PRP	44.54	59.54	59	39
AVC-JE-NUS-PRP	36.78	54.40	52.47	28.79
VQVC-W-NUS-PRP	24.56	45.53	39.47	15.24
USVC	44.25	38.05	56.0	36.02

Table 3: The median values of comparing the same singer with converted and original voices. The GE2E column represents an analysis of the audio with GE2E embeddings, and JE column the same but with JE embeddings.

Chapter 5

Discussion

The outcome of this work was expected to be not a significant improvement in the Singing Voice Conversion field, especially in the subsection of it with zero-shot voice conversion. It was a risky decision to explore a topic that, to our knowledge, was not yet published anywhere. Analyzing and experimenting with the current state of the art methods for speech or voice conversion in the context of Zero-Shot Singing Voice Conversion is the main contribution of this work. We hope that this thesis and similar works will be an initial step for future advancements in the field of Zero-Shot Singing Voice Conversion where the architectures will be developed specifically for this task instead of adapting existing methods for speech voice conversion.

5.1 Future work

We left out the exploration of many things during our research. One experiment that we would want to do in the future is to train GE2E speaker encoder with singing data or perhaps to make the use of the existing pre-trained models on big speech corpus, we could employ the Transfer Learning technique to train existing models with singing data. Another problem that makes the results of our experiments hard to compete with the other state of the art voice conversion models is that we use WORLD vocoder to synthesize the audio. Most of the new works utilize Neural Vcoders such as WaveNet or WaveGlow[56] they have a superior audio quality over

WORLD vocoder but suffer from slower generation speed. However, some methods look promising in terms of computation and that would be another experiment to try. In particular, we are interested in trying Parallel WaveGAN[57] which can generate a 24 kHz speech waveform 28.68 times faster than realtime on a single GPU environment.

We also would want to investigate architectural changes in the AutoVC model. For instance, instead of static singer embeddings that are pre-computed before the training, we could follow a similar idea as in VQVC+ and have a trainable speaker encoder that would update the weights based on the conversion results. The rationale for this change is that the speaker encoders we used were built for the speaker or singer identifications which are different from the voice conversion task. Last but not least, is to try to increase the dataset with data augmentation and to use special training techniques for the conversion or translation tasks. This is why, in some cases, USVC performed better than our models despite having only NUS dataset – they have employed during the training stage back-translation and the mixup technique, and other data augmentation techniques. That means in practice, they had more data than just the NUS dataset. Our hypothesis if we try the same techniques we could increase the quality of our results as well.

5.2 Conclusions

We show that it is possible to adapt existing methods of Zero-Shot Speech Voice Conversion to the case of Zero-Shot Singing Voice conversion. We also analyze the state of the art speaker embeddings in the context of split speech and singing data as well as in the mixed voices. And find that embeddings models that are trained on a larger data corpus perform better with the separate data. Also, when an embedding model is trained with only speech or singing data it is less applicable to the mixed data. The subjective evaluation shows that AutoVC based model trained with GE2E speaker embeddings performs the best in terms of timbre conversion, melody matching, language content preservation, and overall audio quality.

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